

Supplemental Figure 1. Cumulative incidence of patients requiring additional treatment with radiotherapy and/or BRAF/MEK inhibitor targeted therapy after surgery. Kaplan-Meier representation of the overall cohort of patient.

Supplemental Figure 2. Kaplan-Meier representation of progression free survival (remission) in patients with craniopharyngioma, according to MRI types (A, B and C).